

EARTH SCIENCES

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF MODERN GEOGRAPHICAL RESEARCH

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ОСНОВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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Abstract

As in any science, geography cannot be assumed without research. As the research of science becomes necessary, its research methods are updated and improved. In the field of geographical science, researches are conducted using modern new research methods. Therefore, the study of the modern research direction of geography can be considered one of the priority directions of science.

Аннотация

Как и в любой науке, географию нельзя предположить без исследований. По мере того, как исследование науки становится необходимым, ее методы исследования обновляются и совершенствуются. В области географических наук исследования проводятся с использованием современных новых методов исследования. Поэтому изучение современного исследовательского направления географии можно считать одним из приоритетных направлений науки.

Keywords: Science, research, GIS, geography, modern, method

Ключевые слова: наука, исследования, ГИС, география, современные, метод

The presence of breakthroughs in science, engineering and technology has created the need for innovation in the science of geography. The use of modern technologies, especially in the conduct of research in geography, has led to important results.

Economic geography, which studies production areas, gradually added the geography of social areas to its research object. The expansion of the essence of science required a change in its name. Therefore, the name "Economic and Social Geography" was born, and since 1979 the Higher Attestation Commission approves the awarding of the titles of Candidate of Sciences and Doctor of Sciences in this specialty.

The concept of geographical culture, used in modern times, is interpreted by V.P. Maksakovski in a narrow and broad sense. In the first case, we are talking about the professional culture of specialist geographers, their deep knowledge of the main theoretical and applied issues of their science. In a broad sense, geographical culture means that every citizen of a modern civilized society has the necessary amount of knowledge in the field of geography. At this junction, the teacher occupies an intermediate position, acting, on the one hand, as a connoisseur of geography, and on the other, as a distributor of mass geographical culture among young people. Geographic culture includes four main elements:

1. Geographical view of the world;
2. Geographical thinking;
3. Geographical methods;
4. Geographic language [2, 5].

Famous scientists also spoke about the role of geography in the development of human culture and education. In recent years, geographical culture has been significantly enriched with elements of economic, cartographic and, most importantly, ecological culture. Ecological culture is characterized by the joint efforts of all people living on our planet to preserve the environment and pass it on to future generations.

An increase in the **anthropogenic load** on natural complexes leads to the spread of environmental pollution dangerous for humans to larger areas. Therefore, there is a great need for the publication of more literature related to these problems that are relevant to the life of mankind. Global problems of a crisis nature (geographic-environmental, demographic, water, energy, food, mineral resources) are studied more from the point of view of the safe living of mankind [8].

In recent years, the demand for **mapping products** has grown significantly due to educational, political and research needs. New thematic and regional maps were compiled, geoinformatics technologies were applied. In a word, the maps have become more meaningful and massive due to the areas of application. Based on the widespread use of dynamic geographical images, computers, slide films, educational geographical films, etc., a new video-cartography section has been created. However, it should be noted that there is also a fear that cartography will break away from its geographical basis and fall under the influence of geoinformatics. This may create a danger of its dissolution in the composition of geoinformatics. Therefore, in geography, the main attention should be focused on

the wide use of information and automation tools as a method in cartography [1, 4].

There is more innovation and advancement happening in **environmental mapping**. Space-based images of Earth and its large regions at different heights and at different time periods provide detailed information about environmental conditions. The production of environmental maps based on geographic information systems (GIS) about countries and their regions is expanding. Compiled electronic maps and atlases dedicated to the analysis of the development of territories and assessment of their condition. Such maps also display the use of natural resources, population dynamics, problems of balanced (sustainable) development of regions, etc.

There is no break in the geographical study of the Earth. Although new lands are not being discovered, the secrets of the World Ocean are being revealed: the exploration of physical and chemical composition of ocean water, its flow, reproduction, behavior, protection of fish and other animal species that play an important role in human nutrition, global environmental conditions of the ocean, etc. is continuing [2, 3].

Geographers understand and study the interaction between nature and society. The study of the Earth in space is gaining momentum. The science of space geography is emerging. Using advanced and more accurate methods of this science, hurricanes and meteorological phenomena on Earth are predicted, the location of settlements, industrial areas, crops and transport routes are studied.

By the old methods, neither by a map nor by a globe, it is impossible to acquire knowledge as extensive as that which cosmic geography gives. For this, a large amount of satellite images and materials taken over decades at different heights and in different lighting conditions are more useful. These materials are quite enough to build the modern geography of the rotating Earth, from the point of view of a real "globe". Straits, oceans, seas, islands, mountains and deserts on earth have a completely different appearance on the Cosmic Globe. These images bring the Earth's color mosaic to life like a large film strip. When you look

from space, you clearly see that there is nothing accidental in nature and everything lives according to its own law. From the spacecraft, you can see the simultaneous passage of the seasons in the northern and southern hemispheres of the Earth by changing the color of plants. The connection between the geological formation close to the surface and the general picture of the landscape formed on it are clearly visible. By studying the tectonic structure of the terrain from space, it is possible to determine the right directions for mineral exploration [6, 7].

With the help of images and information obtained in space, the study of the ecological state of the Earth as a whole and in individual regions is of exceptional importance.

Recent achievements include the creation of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based on space materials. Digital maps made with this system include extensive geographic information: topography, rainfall, temperature, population density, flora and fauna, etc.

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